

IHI 101112022 - iCARE4CVD

INDIVIDUALISED CARE FROM EARLY RISK
OF CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE TO
ESTABLISHED HEART FAILURE

WP2 – Federated Data Management

D2.2 Federated Data analysis Architecture – Part 2

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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable focuses on reporting on the Federated Data Infrastructure for iCARE4CVD. The deliverable reports on the work performed within the first eighteen months of the project. This deliverable provides an update of the first architecture as defined in Deliverable D2.1. We maintain the structure of Deliverable D2.1 but update the contents to reflect the current developments.

In this document we describe the three-layered architecture. We describe each layer in terms of components and how they connect to one another. We explain the 3 layers in terms of the three main components:

1. **The Cohort Explorer** – a tool for exploring and mapping the data into the iCARE4CVD platform
2. **The blockchain monitoring** – a tool to enable data owners to manage their own cohorts and
3. **Data clean rooms** – offered by the Decentriq platform where the data are stored under the control of data owners and are analysed by researchers in respect to data sharing agreements.

2 Introduction

Our architecture has three layers, each designed to protect patient data privacy while enabling flexible analysis (Fig. 1). The Cohort explorer UI based on knowledge graphs provides a unified interface for exploring cohorts on a meta-data level, making it easy for analysts to identify studies and datasets relevant to their research questions. In the analysis layer, LUCE Blockchain [8] platform handles data permissions and holds data sharing agreements. Decentriq Data Clean Rooms ensure secure data analysis while maintaining regulatory compliance. Our architecture enables researchers to analyse data efficiently and securely while allowing partners providing data (data providers) to maintain control over processing of such data and preserve patient privacy.

Fig 1. Technical Architecture Components

1. In the Cohort Explorer, metadata (i.e. the variables and endpoints collected in the study, and their types) is mapped into a common ontology and made available to the researchers for identifying relevant cohorts (no patient data, only meta-data).
2. Data sharing parameters are defined in the blockchain platform, ensuring data sharing transparency and compliance to data sharing agreements.

3. Encrypted data can be analysed while remaining fully under the data owners' control. For a deeper dive on what this means see the DCR Data Protection whitepaper [6], [7]

From a user experience perspective, there are two main types of users: data owners (also known as data custodians or data providers) and researchers (also known as data requesters or data analysts). In general, users of iCARE4CVD go through the following process which is also illustrated in Fig 2:

1. Users connect to the cohort explorer UI and create an account
2. If they are data owners, they upload their data dictionary (metadata). The cohort explorer validates the metadata file and helps data owners to complete the mapping into a knowledge graph.
3. Data owner users log into the Decentriq environment where they get the encryption toolkit to upload their data to a Data Clean Room. This process of connecting the data is entirely managed between the data owner and Decentriq's platform, with no involvement of the cohort explorer. Decentriq's platform encrypts the data as soon as it is uploaded to the DCR.
4. Researchers (data analyst) can form questions in the cohort explorer. Additionally, they can develop analysis scripts that run on the encrypted data in Data Clean Rooms
5. Data owners approve the analyses computations/scripts.

Fig: 2 High Level Component Interactions in iCARE4CVD

6. Approved analysis results are retrieved without the raw data ever being exposed or compromised/viewed or leaving the DCR. The analysis results and visualizations are incorporated into the cohort explorer and can be used by other users to identify potential relevance.

7. Blockchain keeps an immutable record of all the actions that happen to the data (i.e User X explored the data Y, User X submitted a request for analysis etc), using the DCR log obtained from Decentriq's API

A technical factsheet of the main components of the architecture and their interactions was sent to all partners. This summary has included it in the Annexes section.

3 Background

The three layers of iCARE4CVD require three different technologies. In Layer 1, the Cohort Explorer, ultimately helps in the building of Knowledge Graphs (a semantic structure describing the data and their interpretation at a high level), Layer 2, requires a blockchain network for defining a mechanism for capturing and managing individual data sharing consent in a trusted and decentralized way, Layer 3 is the actual data layer, it used confidential computing which is a mechanism defined within the data clean rooms, a space where the data is fully controlled by the data owner.

In this section we will explain and motivate in detail the use of these three core technologies.

3.1 Data Harmonisation and Knowledge Graphs

Harmonizing clinical data across diverse cohorts is one of the most persistent challenges in healthcare research. Each dataset often emerges from a different institutional, national, or clinical context, and as a result, the way variables are labelled, coded, and structured tends to vary significantly. Even seemingly similar variables—like blood pressure, medication use, or diagnostic categories—may follow different conventions, units, or terminologies. This inconsistency creates barriers when trying to conduct cross-study analysis or build generalized models, especially in the context of federated research environments where data is not centralized but remains within institutional boundaries.

A knowledge graph-based approach offers a more flexible and semantically rich way to address these issues [15]. By using a graph structure grounded in ontologies and standard vocabularies, we can represent not only the variables themselves but also the relationships between them—whether those relationships are hierarchical, contextual, or domain-specific. This becomes particularly powerful when mapping variables across datasets that differ in granularity or semantics. For instance, aligning "dual antiplatelet therapy" from one study with two separate medication fields in another becomes more manageable when the model understands their shared therapeutic context. The graph not only links the data but captures the logic behind their connection [16].

In federated healthcare research, semantic harmonization is not just a technical requirement—it's foundational for enabling privacy-preserving, large-scale analysis. Since data remains at the source, we need a shared understanding of the metadata to ask meaningful questions across sites [17]. A knowledge graph doesn't replace local models but acts as a semantic overlay, allowing queries, cohort definitions, or harmonized variable views to be expressed in a common conceptual space. This is particularly important in projects dealing with cohort data collected over time, across institutions, or through national registries—each with its own metadata quirks.

Ultimately, moving from rigid ETL (Extract, Transform Load) based pipelines to graph-based harmonization provides a path toward scalability, transparency, and reasoning. It allows for reusability of mappings, automated detection of similar variables, and a deeper alignment between human-understandable clinical logic and machine-executable data models. For integrating data and harmonize metadata from various studies, this has been the foundation that doesn't rely on any one data standard like OMOP or FHIR but is instead designed to integrate across them—supporting a genuinely flexible and ontology-driven ecosystem for clinical research.

3.2 Blockchain and Smart Contracts in iCARE4CVD

Why a blockchain network? Blockchain technology provides a decentralized and tamper-resistant system for managing access to health data:

- Decentralized: means a system where no single entity has control of all data, and,
- Tamper-resistant means that the data are protected against unauthorized modifications

Blockchains address key limitations of traditional centralized data repositories, which often struggle with access control, compliance enforcement, and transparency. In conventional healthcare systems, patient records and research datasets are typically stored in isolated databases managed by individual organizations. This centralized model introduces challenges in data sharing across organisations. Shared data repositories (i.e when data from different organisations are placed on a single server to be shared across organisations) on the other hand, increase the risk of unauthorized modifications limit traceability, and it creates difficulties to ensure who has control of the access policies and to trust that they are consistently enforced.

How a blockchain network works? By contrast, blockchain operates as a distributed ledger (a replicated and synchronized record of transactions across multiple participants in a network), ensuring that no single entity unilaterally controls stored data. Each transaction captures some interaction between participants (e.g. the participant A accessed the data of participant B). Transactions are cryptographically secured (with encryption techniques), and once recorded, it becomes immutable (cannot be altered or deleted). Transactions are added based on a contract determining if the transaction can happen and a consensus mechanism. The consensus mechanism refers to a protocol used to ensure that network participants validate transactions before they are written into the blockchain). This process guarantees data integrity by preventing unauthorized modifications. Additionally, smart contracts (programs deployed on the blockchain that enforce predefined rules without manual intervention) in the blockchain enable automated and controlled data sharing. These contracts ensure that access policies are enforced transparently and consistently, reducing reliance on centralized intermediaries while enhancing accountability and efficiency in managing healthcare data permissions.

Within the iCARE4CVD, the integration of blockchain is done through extending the LUCE blockchain platform [18]. LUCE is a platform defined to enhance the governance of health data sharing. It ensures that data access policies of data owners are enforced in a cryptographically verifiable manner. Using smart contracts, LUCE allow data owners to define precise access conditions, specifying who can use their data, for what purpose, and under what constraints [19]. These rules are automatically enforced, preventing unauthorized use and ensuring compliance with regulatory requirements.

From a blockchain perspective, every data-related action—such as access requests, analysis submissions, and approvals—can be immutably recorded, enhancing transparency, accountability, and trust in federated data-sharing infrastructures. This decentralized approach mitigates key challenges associated with centralized models, providing a more scalable and secure foundation for collaborative healthcare research. Table 1 highlights key features of the iCARE4CVD approach with blockchain and how it addresses some of the challenges faced by conventional federated data-sharing models.

Table 1: Key Features of the iCARE4CVD Approach with Blockchain Compared to Conventional Federated Data-Sharing Models

Feature	Conventional Federated Data Sharing	iCARE4CVD with Blockchain
Data Owner Control	Limited; relies on predefined agreements and institutional trust	Enhanced through enforceable smart contracts that define and automate policies

Transparency of Data Usage	Varies; tracking depends on institutional policies and access logs	High transparency through an immutable and auditable blockchain ledger
Auditability of Access	Typically relies on institutional logs, which may not be fully transparent	Comprehensive and tamper-proof audit trail of all data interactions recorded on the blockchain
Enforcement of Sharing Agreements	Based on policy documents and legal contracts; enforcement is manual	Automated enforcement through smart contracts on the blockchain
Consent Management	Often static, requiring manual updates and institutional intervention	Dynamic consent model allowing personalized and evolving preferences
Security of Governance Records	Depends on institutional access control mechanisms	Decentralized and cryptographically secured blockchain ledger

A core function of LUCE is to manage data sharing agreements, allowing data owners to define precise access policies that specify authorized researchers, permitted analyses, and licensing terms such as redistribution restrictions or consent requirements. Once established, these policies will be immutably recorded on the blockchain, ensuring transparency, auditability, and tamper resistance, thereby creating a verifiable record of who accessed what data under which conditions.

Since sensitive patient data remains within Data Clean Rooms, researchers will interact only with metadata and aggregated results. By embedding data access control, consent management, and accountability into iCARE4CVD, LUCE will provide a structured and scalable framework for secure data governance.

3.3 Data Clean Rooms

Decentriq is a cloud service software platform that provides a unique promise: data can be used for collaboration without being shared, data can only be used for a specific limited purpose, and compliance can be remotely verified. This is true even when the data is used in collaboration with other organizations. The original owner retains full control over the data during the entire lifecycle and can prove that it was only used for an explicit and limited purpose. This provides tangible benefits to organizations that use Decentriq's platform:

1. The platform drastically reduces the risk that a researcher mishandles or leaks data.
2. Participants can extend the scope for which they can compliantly process personal data under GDPR and other regulations by eliminating the need to share personal data, reducing the risk of misuse.
3. Participants can collaborate with other Data Owners without having to trust anyone with their data, enabling the joint use of business secrets even between competitors.

To achieve this, DECENTRIQ relies on cloud computers that are based on Confidential Computing.

Understanding Confidential Computing

Confidential Computing represents a paradigm shift in data security by addressing a critical vulnerability in traditional cloud computing: the protection of data while it's being processed.

Traditional data security focuses on two states:

- **Data at rest:** Protected through encryption when stored on disks or databases
- **Data in transit:** Protected through encrypted connections (like HTTPS/TLS) when moving across networks

However, a significant vulnerability remains: **data in use** - the moment when data must be decrypted in memory for computation or analysis. During this phase, data was traditionally vulnerable to access by privileged users like system administrators, cloud providers, or sophisticated attackers who gain access to the memory of the system.

Confidential Computing closes this gap by protecting data even during computation through hardware-based Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs). These secure enclaves provide:

- **Hardware-level isolation:** Computations run in protected memory regions isolated from the operating system, hypervisor, and other processes
- **Memory encryption:** Data remains encrypted in memory and is only decrypted within the CPU, inaccessible even to the system administrators
- **Attestation:** Cryptographic verification that the correct, unmodified code is running in the secure environment

This technology enables a new level of assurance where not even Decentriq, cloud providers, or system administrators can access sensitive data at any point in its lifecycle - a critical requirement for handling sensitive healthcare data across organizational boundaries.

Confidential Computing in Healthcare Data Collaboration

For healthcare research like iCARE4CVD, this technology is transformative because:

1. **Sovereignty with collaboration:** Data custodians (hospitals, research institutions) can maintain complete control over their sensitive patient data while still enabling its use for collaborative research.
2. **Regulatory compliance:** Facilitates compliance with GDPR by minimizing data transfer and ensuring purpose limitation.
3. **Cross-institutional analysis:** Enables the combination of datasets across multiple institutions without exposing the raw data, critical for developing better predictive models and treatments.
4. **Verifiable privacy guarantees:** Participants can cryptographically verify that their data is being used only for approved purposes through remote attestation - transforming trust requirements from "trust us" to "verify us."

To provide these fully verifiable data protection guarantees, Decentriq implements [Confidential Computing](#) through hardware technologies like Intel Software Guard Extensions [11], AMD Secure Encrypted Virtualization with Secure Nested Paging [12], and other emerging technologies. The platform creates a secure computational environment where data remains protected even during analysis, ensuring that even with physical access to the servers, the data remains inaccessible to unauthorized parties.

3.3.1 Data Clean Room Abstraction

Decentriq enables users to collaborate on data with the guarantee that their contributed data sets can only be used for the explicitly specified intended purpose. The platform uses the metaphor of a **Data Clean Room**, a highly controlled environment free from outside influence, to describe a specific act of collaboration.

The key element that ties a clean room together is a data structure called the **Data Clean Room Configuration**. This data structure contains the essential terms of the collaboration:

1. Table Schemas and File Definitions - what data will be included and how it will be structured.
2. Computations - what operations will be performed on the data.
3. User Permissions - who is responsible for contributing data (Data Owner) and who can see the results (Researcher).
4. Authentication Root - The root certificate authority used for user authentication.
5. Attestation Specification - other technical details required to ensure that the configuration is unambiguous and complete. This includes the verification policy for the hardware.

The Data Clean Room Configuration ties these parameters together into a verifiable format which allows each participant to review and understand the scope of collaboration. The Decentriq platform uses cryptographic protocols to indelibly bind these parameters to the code that executes them. This is the “contract” for the collaboration – readable by humans, but enforceable by the platform.

4 Methods

In this section we will provide an overall architecture and will further develop the 3 components of the architecture, namely: the Cohort Explorer/ Knowledge graph: the LUCE blockchain, and the Data Clean Room Component.

4.1 ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW

Fig 3 depicts a detailed general architecture that includes the three layers shown in Fig.2. Three main users are shown to be interacting in the platform: Data owner/provider, Admin and the Researcher/Data Requester. For simplicity we will refer to the users as data owners, admin and researchers. Data owners are asked to complete a data dictionary template prior to engaging with the platform. The data dictionary template was developed as part of WP1 and consist of various fields that capture the variables in the cohort, their description and their representation. For more details, please refer to the deliverables of WP1.

Fig 3: iCARE4CVD General Architecture.

Fig 3 depicts how a data owner, after completing the data dictionary, will interact with the iCARE4CVD platform via the Cohort Explorer. The Cohort Explorer exposes a Frontend to engage with the iCARE4CVD users. Data dictionaries are checked for errors, missing fields or wrong values. The errors of the data dictionary are shown to the user (typically the data owner or the admin). The users can update the data dictionary and come back to upload it to the platform.

Data owners can specify for which research purposes the cohort can be shared. Within the Blockchain Layer, a transparent monitoring and data management process is established. If needed, and in accordance with the consent agreement, data owners can limit researchers to perform questions within the scope of one disease. Furthermore, cohort access can be limited by geographically (i.e. only researchers within the EU). The blockchain layer can enforce these mechanisms dynamically. The cohort explorer interacts with the blockchain layer, prior to enabling the researcher to access the cohorts in the Decentriq Data Clean Room.

Finally, the cohort's data will be connected by the data owner in the data clean room (DCR). The researcher selects the cohorts in the cohort explorer. The cohort explorer will send the information about which variables of the cohorts the researcher would like to access. The researcher can then interact in the DCR to specify what they would like to do, to create the analytical scripts and request permissions to run them.

In the following sections we further explain each layer in more details.

4.2 Layer 1: Data Integration Layer

4.2.1 The Cohort Explorer

The Cohort Explorer provides four main functionalities:

- 1. Browsing the available cohorts, their descriptions and meta-data,
- 2. Querying for specific cohorts based on: type of cohort, type of study, the data provider, and desired features (i.e endpoints),
- 3. Comparing cohorts for the purpose of combined data analysis, and
- 4. Sharing and viewing summary statistics and visualizations pertaining to the cohort variables.

This layer (shown in purple in Fig. 3) handles metadata (descriptions of the cohorts and/or datasets as provided by the users of the platform), and the summary output of the clean room

In Fig 3, we show the **Cohort Explorer Frontend**. This is the main interface of iCARE4CVD. Via this interface, users of iCARE4CVD connect and can see summary data from the cohorts as they are described by data owners.

The **Cohort Explorer API** (also known as the back end) mediates the interactions between the users and the system. It ensures that users are authenticated at log-in, it receives Data Dictionaries which are then displayed in the Cohort Explorer Frontend. The cohort explorer API supports the following:

- **User log-in and authentication:** Users of iCARE4CVD login with their Decentriq account (OAuth based authentication). Only accounts with the required permissions will be able to access the platform. Members of the iCare4CVD project need to contact Decentriq to request an account prior to being able to interact with the platform. In technical terms, once the user is logged in through the (Decentriq) OAuth provider, the backend generates an encrypted JASON Web Token (JWT) [9], which is passed to the frontend using HTTP-only cookies.
- **Uploading and storing metadata:** Users are provided with a data dictionary. Such data dictionary is aimed at capturing metadata of the various cohorts/datasets. To date, the assumption is that cohorts are organized in one table (i.e. one csv file), this is in line with the information collected by the iCARE4CVD partners. The Cohort Explorer API performs checks on the data dictionary to ensure that the data dictionaries are filled in and do not contain errors.
- **Mapping of the cohort variables.** Currently, the mapping is automated via AI tool integration. This integrated tool helps to identify potential OMOP identifiers [10] for each concept, its categorical values, visit and measurement information. A variable could be mapped to single or composite codes depending on the contextual factors e.g. body position for blood pressure measurement. A mapping mechanism allows the user (admin or data owner) to identify mapping IDs for their cohort variables. Mappings are further explained in Section 4.2.2. Consistency in mapping is achieved of the project by: i) utilizing AI tools to automate mappings, ii) Fixing the IDs for common variables; ii). Enabling admin mapping; iv) Enabling key data scientists in the project to review existing mappings.
- **Storing the mappings** into a structured knowledge graph. The identified mappings are stored into a triple store. As more cohorts are incorporated in iCARE4CVD, we identify new concepts and include them as variable instances in the ontology of the knowledge graph. We use BFO [14] as a basis for defining such ontology where each variable is linked to other medical terminologies without defining concepts in the ontology (i.e. from SNOMED, LOINC). In section 4.2.3 we expand our discussion with more information on the semantic model of iCARE4CVD.
- **Querying Cohorts:** Cohorts that are described (with the data dictionaries) in the system, can be explored by researchers. Via the cohort explorer frontend, users can view the cohorts. A simple filtering has already been implemented to filter cohorts by type or by specific variables. Moreover, the ontology model enables complex queries where similar studies with common measured variables can be identified.
- **Merging cohorts:** This is a functionality that it is currently being developed in the cohort explorer. Some level of harmonization mapping of two given cohorts is possible via knowledge graphs exploration tool which represents all studies and their data dictionaries in semantically coherent manner. This tool is under development and requires further testing and validation At this time, merging of variables is possible only in DCR, however, the semantic layer can support it, by identifying common variables (as briefly described above).
- **Request Access to data:** Via the cohort explorer, users can add the cohorts of interest and request access to the data in a data clean room. The request to access relevant cohorts is recorded in the blockchain. Should the purpose of study be in-line with the data collection purposes of the study to be accessed, then the permissions is granted. A structure of the query (the variables that need to be accessed in each cohort) is sent to the data clean room which handles the rest of the interactions between the researcher and the iCARE4CVD platform. This aspect is best explained in section 4.3.

Fig 4. Modular Framework Stepwise Workflow for Mapping of Common Data Elements Using RAG

4.2.2 Semantic Mappings of Cohort Variables

Problem and Background: The standardization of clinical data elements (CDEs) is a critical challenge in iCARE4CVD. The strategic use of data from different sources (electronic health records (EHRs), clinical trials, and observational studies) is essential for advancing clinical CVD research and improving healthcare outcomes. However, this is a significant challenge in data standardization and integration across diverse healthcare systems. A key problem is the inconsistent representation and interpretation of clinical concepts across datasets, necessitating concept linking to achieve semantic consistency. This task, also termed entity linking and entity normalization of clinical/biomedical labels, is crucial for data interoperability required in our federated platform. Poor concept linking practices lead to risks such as discrepancies in patient cohort definitions and inconsistencies in the recording of diagnoses. These issues can impede accurate data integration, reproducibility or results, and reliable healthcare decision-making.

While atomic CDEs (representing a single characteristic) can often be mapped to established terminologies, composite CDEs (capturing multiple interdependent attributes) introduce additional complexities due to the relationships among their attributes, which are often not adequately considered by existing concept linking approaches. Therefore, a systematic and rigorous approach is required to harmonize these data elements in heterogeneous datasets to enable accurate interpretation, transparency, integration, and reuse across diverse healthcare systems and research studies.

Methodology

In iCARE4CVD we developed an AI tool called CDE-Mapper, that utilizes a Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) approach combined with Large Language Models (LLMs) to automate the linking of clinical data elements (CDEs) aka variables to controlled vocabularies. The goal of this standardization is to ensure consistent and comprehensive patient information across various healthcare systems, which is often hindered by the varying representations and complex structures of CDEs. Poor concept linking can lead to significant discrepancies, impeding data integration, research reproducibility, and reliable healthcare decision-making.

The architecture of CDE-Mapper is a modular RAG system as shown in Fig 4. The stepwise workflow involves several key components:

Input Data Dictionary: The framework standardizes the input into a data dictionary format, which can include descriptions, categories, measurement units, formulas, and visit information for each variable. The description of the variable is mandatory, while other components are optional.

Linking Rules: These rules provide a structured and dynamically configurable approach to link clinical terms to appropriate source vocabularies based on data types (e.g., link diagnoses to SNOMED CT, medications to RxNorm/ATC, and lab results to LOINC/SNOMED).

Query Decomposition: This module enhances the original query and breaks down composite queries into simpler, manageable components, outputting a structured format (e.g., JSON) where each component is treated as a subquery (e.g., base entity, associated entities, categories, unit, method, formula). This decomposition is guided by in-context learning using task descriptions, original queries, and relevant examples curated with domain experts

Knowledge Retriever: This component employs an ensemble candidate retrieval strategy to find the most accurate match within a knowledge base of over three million concepts from various controlled vocabularies (SNOMED, LOINC, ICD, ATC, MedDRA, RxNorm/RxNorm-Extension, MeSH, UCUM, and OMOP Extension and Genomics). It uses a dual embedding strategy with SPLADE for exact matches of canonical concepts and SapBERT for nuanced, contextually rich queries. The retriever merges results from both model.

Knowledge Filtering: This module filters the retrieved candidates to enhance accuracy and precision by discarding irrelevant or semantically misaligned candidates using metadata-based filtering rules and a similarity thresholds

Two-Step Reranking: This module further refines the candidate list. Step 1 involves an LLM reranking candidates based on relevance scores. Step 2 classifies the top candidates into relevance categories (not relevant, partially relevant, highly relevant, exact match) and assigns scores. A self-consistency prompting strategy is used to obtain confidence scores for each candidate across multiple prompts.

Knowledge Reservoir: Correctly predicted and expert-validated concepts (through a human-in-the-loop approach) are stored in a structured format (dictionary for direct lookup or triple store for composite CDEs) to reduce LLM inference time for future applications. OMOP IDs are used for better disambiguation across vocabularies.

CDE-Mapper is used because existing mapping methods often struggle with CDEs that have varying representations and complex structures, particularly composite CDEs. Traditional rule-based systems and many deep learning-based methods are often optimized for atomic CDEs and can face scalability issues with large vocabularies. LLMs offer potential but lack intrinsic domain knowledge and can struggle with specialized terminologies. RAG addresses these limitations by combining the generative capabilities of LLMs with dynamically retrieved domain-specific knowledge from controlled vocabularies, ensuring up-to-date and accurate concept linking. CDE-Mapper further enhances this by its modular design to handle CDE complexity through query decomposition, improve retrieval accuracy with ensemble methods and knowledge filtering, and ensure high-quality linking through a validated knowledge reservoir and a two-step reranking process. This leads to improved data harmonization, which is crucial for advancing clinical decision support systems and research.

CDE-Mapper is available to data owners to automate the mapping of variables. New data dictionaries are filled by the CDE-Mapper. The mappings are further checked and approved by human experts.

4.2.3 OMOP Semantic Model: Ontology

Formal ontologies have become a mainstay in the codification of medical knowledge, enabling not only reasoned data analysis but also the reuse and sharing of data across systems. The Ontology for Biomedical

Investigations (OBI) and the Ontology of Biological and Clinical Statistics (OBCS) capture aspects of study specification and statistical analysis, respectively, while the Statistical Methods Ontology (STATO) and its extension OBCS focuses on statistical methodologies. Other ontologies, such as the Clinical Trial Ontology and Cohort Ontology, address specific study designs but lack broader integration with clinical study metadata and patient-level data harmonization. Simultaneously, relational database models like the OMOP Common Data Model [13] have been recognized for their practicality in organizing and standardizing EHR data. Recent studies suggest that OMOP's content coverage surpasses that of other common data models, demonstrating its effectiveness in the field.

Ontology Model Overview:

The primary goal of CDIO is to develop a unified ontological framework integrating study metadata, observational data, and statistical analyses. Key objectives include enabling advanced queries, supporting interoperability, and facilitating secondary research use in meta-analyses and predictive modelling. The short-term goal focuses on drafting the initial ontology and testing core clinical variables, while the long-term vision includes expanding ontology coverage, enhancing metadata governance, and promoting adoption across research networks.

By structuring study variables, harmonizing metadata, and linking observational data to clinical terminologies, CDIO supports data standardization and interoperability. It enables exploratory data analysis, statistical profiling, and automated reasoning for cohort selection and study integration. This framework ensures efficient and scalable research data harmonization across multi-center studies.

Our proposed Clinical Data Integration Ontology (CDIO) integrates foundational ontologies, including **BFO** for structural consistency, **OBI** for study design representation, **STATO** for statistical methodologies and Data Use ontology (DUO) for permission specification. The primary classes in CDIO include:

- **Study Design Specification:** Captures metadata related to the study protocol, including eligibility criteria, primary outcomes, and temporal structure.
- **Permission specification:** **With respect to each study, its permission specifications can be defined including data use and data permission.**
- **Data Element:** Represents a standardized unit of information, specifying attributes such as additional factors considered while taking measurement, measurement units, permissible values, and categorical classifications.
- **Variable:** Represents study variables which denotes some data element. We have created distinct concepts to represent data element vs variables according to NCIT data element definition. However often they are used interchangeably. Therefore, we connect them via denote relationship.
- **Data Item:** An observed value instance associated with a data element, linked to a specific patient or study participant.
- **Participant Role:** Defines roles within the study (e.g., control group, intervention group) and their relationship to observations.

CDIO reused BFO relationships in restrictive manner (minimal predicates) to structure semantic connections between entities. Most concepts representation is captured with following relationships:

- **is_about:** Links an information object to another information object. For example email address is about some person.
- **has_participant:** Connects a process to a participant role.
- **Is_duration_of** Defines relationships between entities and the time measurement datum.
- **is_specified_output_of / is_specified_input_of:** Used to model processes and their relationship to other entities such as information objects. For example, variable is participant with role 'is specified input of' in

be performed on a cohort. In this layer, we can manage these permissions to create a broad transparency level on how the cohorts are used by other organisations. In the following we describe all these aspects in more detail:

4.3.1 LUCE Blockchain Architecture

In Fig. 3 we show 2 main components of LUCE that interact in the iCARE4CVD framework. The **LUCE blockchain API**, used to transact in the blockchain (insert information into the blockchain layer) and the **Data Sharing Monitoring with Smart Contracts** which consist of pre-established data management rules that are specific to each cohort and controlled by the data owners.

The **LUCE blockchain API**: To interact with LUCE, the Cohort Explorer will use the LUCE blockchain API. This API supports actions tailored to each user role – for instance, it allows data owners to register, publish, update, or remove information about the cohort data, facilitating dynamic data management; Researchers (as Data requesters) can request access to cohort data, and periodically affirm license compliance to secure ongoing access rights, thereby simplifying the process of data utilization; Additionally, LUCE introduces several components to maintain a local overview of the platform's state. In particular, a secure data storage component is responsible for the safe access to datasets, requiring valid LUCE tokens for entry. For user authentication and access control, a user registry contract records all registered blockchain addresses, allowing only verified users to engage with the LUCE Blockchain. Data concerning users (data owners or researchers), is securely stored in a local database (LuceDB). This database mirrors the information held in smart contracts—such as dataset hashes, metadata, license types, intended uses, and user access rights—but also serves as a dynamic cache, facilitating access to data without the need to query the blockchain for each interaction, thus ensuring efficient and seamless user experiences on the platform.

As mentioned, the LUCE blockchain leverages smart contracts to automate consent management for data sharing. Specifically, from the perspective of the smart contract, the process begins with data providers registering their sharing conditions in a structured format called Terms, which captures key parameters such as: (i) Research Purposes: Whether the data can be used for general research, genetic studies, disease-specific investigations, or clinical applications; (ii) Geographic Restrictions: Allowed regions are defined using aggregated group codes and individual country codes, ensuring compliance with jurisdictional regulations; (iii) Disease-Specific Criteria: The contract distinguishes between baseline diseases (strict permissions) and affordable diseases (broader accessibility), allowing providers to define precise research scopes; and (iv) Temporal Constraints: Access to data is restricted based on start date and duration, preventing unauthorized use before or after specified periods. To efficiently encode these conditions, the contract utilizes bitwise flags and mappings, enabling compact storage and fast validation. This structure ensures that policies can be dynamically checked without requiring expensive on-chain storage of large datasets.

Similarly, data requesters submit their intended usage details using the PurposeRequester structure, which includes Boolean indicators for: (a) Research activities, such as methods development, clinical trials, and decision support systems; (b) Data usage conditions, including whether they require profit-driven research, academic use, or non-commercial purposes; and (c) Regulatory constraints, specifying whether formal approvals, collaborations, or security measures are needed. By standardizing these inputs, the contract enables a direct, automated matching process between provider permissions and requester intent.

Once both stakeholders have submitted their terms, the smart contract performs a sequence of automated checks to determine whether access should be granted. These validations ensure that data is only shared under explicitly authorized conditions: (i) Purpose Validation: A bitwise operation verifies that the requester's intended use is a subset of the provider's allowed purposes. If there is any mismatch, access is denied; (ii) Geographic Compliance: The contract compares group and country codes, ensuring that the requester's designated regions are within the provider's approved areas. A combination of iterative checks and bitwise aggregations prevents circumvention of geographic restrictions; (iii) Disease-Specific Authorization:

Both baseline diseases (strict limitations) and affordable diseases (more flexible conditions) are verified to confirm alignment between provider permissions and requester intent; and (iv) Temporal Constraints: The contract enforces start date and duration limits, verifying that the requester's proposed timeline does not precede the provider's authorized start date. Each validation step contributes to a cumulative 32-bit result, where each bit represents a specific policy violation. This aggregated result serves two purposes: (i) If all conditions are satisfied, access is granted; and (ii) If any condition fails, the result pinpoints which policy areas require adjustment, allowing requesters to modify their terms accordingly.

The final step in the process is `AccessData`, the function responsible for consolidating all validation results. If all checks pass, the function returns zero, indicating that access is fully authorized. If any conditions are violated, a non-zero error code is returned, explicitly identifying the unmet requirements. This automated enforcement mechanism ensures that: (a) Data is only accessed under predefined conditions, eliminating unauthorized use; (b) Compliance is strictly enforced without manual oversight or intervention; and (c) Transparency is maintained, as all access attempts and results are permanently recorded on the LUCE blockchain.

Overall, the smart contract in the LUCE blockchain provides a decentralized, automated, and verifiable approach to data-sharing consent management. By integrating bitwise validation mechanisms, dynamic policy registration, and decentralized enforcement, the contract ensures that data-sharing agreements are executed without relying on centralized entities.

Monitoring data Sharing with Smart Contracts:

In LUCE, each cohort/dataset is associated with a unique smart contract, serving multiple critical functions: Firstly, it manages access rights, as set by the data owners, ensuring data is accessed only under agreed licensing terms through binding agreements between data owners and researchers. Secondly, it offers a mechanism for provenance verification, embedding the dataset's hash within the contract to unambiguously establish ownership and protect against data theft and intellectual property violations. Thirdly, the contract enables an immutable history of dataset access, detailing who accessed the data, the duration, and the purpose, which is pivotal for data subjects' right to information and for auditing compliance with licensing terms

The following paragraphs outlines what happens in the blockchain when data is shared or accessed. Such functionalities will be carefully integrated at the later stages of the project.

What happens in the LUCE blockchain when Data Owners Share Data?

The data-sharing process begins with data owners uploading the data dictionary in the cohort explorer front-end. This act is sent to the LUCE platform (not the data dictionary). This will prompt the questions for the data owners on the data re-use terms of the dataset. A smart contract is created encapsulating the link between the data owner, the cohort and the re-use terms of the data. The data owner is recoded in the blockchain with an ID which in blockchain terms is called address. The link between the data owner's name and the address is kept private in the LuceDB. To an external observer, the actions in the system are not identifiable. They can be identified only in the iCARE4CVD platform.

What happens in the LUCE blockchain when Data Requesters Access Data?

Before analysing data in a data clean room, researchers first define their research needs. For example, they may state: I want to perform disease-specific research on heart failure within the next six months, with a non-profit intention. Upon selecting relevant cohorts in the cohort explorer, researchers submit access requests through smart contracts linked to individual cohorts. This process is facilitated by an interaction between the

cohort explorer API and the LUCE API, where the smart contract performs an automated compatibility check between the requested reuse purpose and the original data-sharing conditions set by the data owner. Access is granted only after researchers accept the licensing terms, at which point the smart contract issues a verification token and an access link to the data clean room.

LUCE's smart contract infrastructure ensures that data reuse is continuously monitored beyond initial access. When a data requester agrees to the licensing terms, the smart contract issues an access token, enabling dataset retrieval, renewal, and eventual deletion. The system extends the ERC-1155 standard to transparently manage data ownership and access rights. The access token is time-bound, requiring renewal through the smart contract based on adherence to licensing conditions. If compliance is not maintained, token renewal is denied, effectively revoking access to the dataset. As previously mentioned, LUCE's underlying Solidity contract implements this automated decision-making process by enforcing: (i) Purpose validation to ensure research goals align with dataset permission, (ii) Geographic, disease-specific, and security checks before access approval, and (iii) Smart contract-based enforcement of data-sharing rules through tokenized access, as illustrated in Fig. 6.

Fig 6: Smart Contract-Based Process Flow for Data Access in the LUCE Blockchain Data Sharing System

Agreements between Data Providers and Data Requesters

The consent logic implemented in LUCE's smart contract extends beyond basic binary decisions to accurately reflect the complexity of real-world data-sharing agreements. For instance, LUCE employs the ICD-10 coding system, structured into 26 main categories, each accommodating up to 99 distinct diseases, facilitating precise disease-specific consent management. Within the Solidity smart contract, consent rules are encoded through structured data types, such as Terms, PurposeProvider, and PurposeRequester structures. Each structure captures comprehensive conditions set by data providers and the corresponding requirements from data requesters. For instance, the Terms struct contains elements such as Disease_Category_Affordable, a fixed-size vector (uint128[26]) that represents consent for each ICD-10 disease category with binary precision. A value of '1' at a specific vector position indicates explicit consent for data reuse associated with the corresponding ICD-10 disease category, while '0' indicates no consent (See Fig. 7). The validation of data access requests is managed through bitwise operations, notably using the bitwise AND operator (&) within functions such as CheckDiseaseAffordable. Here, the consent vector provided by the data owner is compared with the consent requirements specified by the researcher. Access is only granted when the result of this bitwise comparison indicates complete compatibility between the researcher's intended usage and the provider's specified consent conditions.

Additionally, the LUCE smart contract implements checks for geographic and temporal constraints. The CheckAreaAffordable and CheckDate functions verify if the geographic and time-related conditions of a request align precisely with the provider's predefined conditions. Purpose validation is similarly handled through the CheckPurpose function, which performs bitwise comparisons to ensure alignment of research goals between providers and requesters.

Fig 7: A Simplified Illustration of Data Consent Matching in LUCE

In Fig. 7, we illustrate a binary sequence representing the data owner's (provider's) consent. The provider's consent vector primarily consists of '1s', signifying approval for most disease categories, except for specific conditions marked by '0s', including the first bit. When the researcher's sequence (denoted as the requester) is introduced, it becomes evident that they seek access to multiple disease codes, as indicated by the '1s' in their sequence. The smart contract processes this access request by executing a bitwise AND operation. If a '0' is present in either the provider's or requester's sequence at a given position, the resulting sequence retains a '0' at that position, preserving the integrity of the provider's consent. For instance, if the first position corresponds to heart failure and the provider has set it to '0', access for heart failure-related data analysis is denied, as reflected in the resulting sequence. Only positions where both the provider's and requester's sequences contain '1s' will remain '1', signifying that the requester is authorized to access those specific disease categories. This bitwise validation mechanism ensures that data sharing adheres to explicit consent conditions while maintaining compliance with data governance policies. A similar approach is used for determining geographic access. For example, the system can assess whether a researcher from the Netherlands meets the predefined conditions for accessing a cohort intended for diabetes research by evaluating the geographic constraints encoded in the smart contract.

To understand the consent logic more formally, we define a set of variables representing the various conditions that must be evaluated for consent:

- P_i : a set of propositions representing the data owner's consent conditions, where i ranges over all primary categories (e.g., open to general research, open to disease specific research, ect).
- S_j : a set of propositions representing the data researcher's purpose statements, where j ranges over all possible purposes (e.g., use for fundamental bio research, use for genetics research).
- R_k : A set of propositions representing additional requirements and restrictions, where k ranges over all additional consent requirements (e.g., geographic restrictions, non-profit use only).

Given these, access is granted if and only if, for all consent conditions P_i , there exists at least one corresponding purpose statement S_j that is true, and all additional requirements R_k are also satisfied. This can be expressed as:

$$\text{AccessGranted} \leftrightarrow \bigwedge_i \left(P_i \rightarrow \bigvee_j S_j \right) \wedge \bigwedge_k R_k$$

Let's understand this with an example:

- P_1 : Data is open to general research.
- S_1 : Researcher intends to use the data for fundamental bio research.
- R_1 : The research must be non-profit.
- R_2 : The research requires geographic restriction compliance.

Now, assuming the data powner has consented to the data being open for general research ($P_1 = \text{True}$) and has specified that the research must be non-profit ($R_1 = \text{True}$) and comply with geographic restrictions ($R_2 = \text{True}$), we can evaluate whether a researcher whose purpose is fundamental bio research ($S_1 = \text{True}$) and meets both R_1 and R_2 is granted access.

4.4 LAYER 3: DATA CLEAN ROOMS

The first two layers handle metadata and access control but do not see or store the cohorts or more broadly speaking the health data themselves. The third layer deals with the sensitive data themselves. Due to the sensitivity of health data, instead of using common cloud-based models to enable data analysis, we rely on the Decentriq platform and their notion of data clean room.

4.4.1 Technical Foundation of Confidential Computing

Data Clean Rooms (DCRs) leverage confidential computing technology to create secure computational environments rather than data repositories. The fundamental innovation of confidential computing is its ability to protect data in all three states:

- **Data at rest:** Protected through encryption when stored on disks
- **Data in transit:** Protected through encrypted connections during network transmission
- **Data in use:** Protected through hardware-based isolation during active computation

This third protection – data in use – represents the critical advancement offered by confidential computing. Traditionally, data had to be decrypted in memory for computation, creating a vulnerability where system administrators, cloud providers, or sophisticated attackers could potentially access sensitive information.

Confidential computing eliminates this vulnerability through hardware-based Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs).

These TEEs implement isolated memory regions protected by specialized processors. In iCARE4CVD, we utilize two primary hardware technologies:

1. **Intel Software Guard Extensions (SGX):** A process-based TEE technology where only the CPU is trusted, with the operating system and similar components running outside the enclave. This approach provides strong security properties with minimal attackable surface, making it ideal for Driver enclaves that coordinate secure computation and protect the most critical encryption keys.
2. **AMD Secure Encrypted Virtualization with Secure Nested Paging (SEV-SNP):** A VM-based TEE technology that extends the enclave to encompass an entire virtual machine including the operating system. This enables secure computations to call the operating system directly, allowing most existing software to run with minimal modification while maintaining security guarantees.

4.4.2 Multi-layered Encryption and Key Management

DCRs implement a sophisticated key management architecture to ensure data security throughout its lifecycle:

1. **Data Keys:** Generated locally by data custodians to encrypt their data before upload. These keys never leave the data custodian's control and are never shared with Decentriq or cloud providers.
2. **Session Keys:** Ephemeral keys established between clients and enclaves using a variant of the SIGMA protocol, an authenticated Diffie-Hellman key agreement. These keys secure the communication channel and are protected by remote attestation.
3. **Cluster Keys:** Shared secrets between enclaves of identical Attestation Specification, allowing distributed computation while maintaining security boundaries. These keys are managed within the TEE and sealed for persistence.
4. **Result Keys:** Used to encrypt computation results that analysts are authorized to access, with decryption managed by the Driver enclave and delivered through the end-to-end encrypted channel.

This key hierarchy ensures that at no point does sensitive data exist in an unprotected form outside the data custodian's environment or the hardware-secured TEE. Even when data is actively processed, it remains encrypted in memory and is only decrypted within the CPU itself, with the applied encryption keys inaccessible even to system administrators.

4.4.3 Remote Attestation Process

Remote attestation is the cryptographic mechanism that validates the integrity and authenticity of the DCR environment. This process allows data custodians to verify that:

1. The computation environment is running on genuine, unmodified confidential computing hardware
2. The exact code specified in the Data Clean Room Configuration is what's being executed
3. The hardware is configured securely with all necessary security patches applied

The attestation process involves:

1. **Measuring the loaded software:** The hardware generates a cryptographic hash (SHA-256 for Intel SGX, SHA-384 for AMD SEV-SNP) of the binary being loaded into the isolated environment.
2. **Generating authenticated evidence:** This measurement is signed with a hardware-bound attestation key that can only be produced by genuine confidential computing hardware.

3. **Verification by the client:** The client checks this evidence against the expected measurement specified in the Attestation Specification and verifies the signature comes from trusted hardware.

This process creates a verifiable chain of trust that extends from the hardware manufacturer to the specific code running in the DCR, enabling data custodians to confirm the security of their data before it's ever provisioned.

4.4.4 Analysis Workflow in DCR

The analysis workflow in a DCR involves several distinct steps that maintain data sovereignty throughout:

Step 1 — Local encryption and upload

Data owners locally encrypt their data with a locally generated encryption key only known to them. This encryption happens entirely on the data owner's system before any data transfer. The encrypted data is then uploaded to the Decentriq platform, but the encryption keys never leave the data custodian's control. The platform uses chunking techniques for integrity verification, splitting datasets into chunks with a maximum size of 8MB, which are hashed using SHA-256 to form a two-level Merkle tree. This cryptographic structure ensures that any modifications to the data would be immediately detectable.

Step 2 — Requesting and approving computations

DCRs operate based on computation nodes rather than direct data access. Two primary types exist:

- **Analysis nodes:** Python, R, SQL environments for data analysis
- **Output privacy nodes:** Specialized nodes for privacy-preserving data exploration
 - **Synthetic data:** Generates statistically similar but non-identifying versions of the data using Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) with differential privacy guarantees
 - **Airlock:** Allows constrained exploration with controlled information release

Each computation request is evaluated by data custodians who can review the purpose, inspect the code, and understand exactly what operations will be performed. The approval mechanism is technically enforced through the DCR Configuration, which binds permissions and constraints cryptographically.

Step 3 — Executing computations and generating results

Once approved, computations execute within the secure TEE where data remains encrypted except during CPU processing. Results are encrypted with dedicated Result Keys and only delivered to authorized analysts. Throughout this process, every operation is cryptographically logged in an append-only audit trail, providing verifiable evidence of all data access.

4.4.5 Security Guarantees

The DCR architecture provides four fundamental security guarantees:

1. **Confidentiality and Integrity:** Data cannot be exfiltrated or modified by unauthorized parties due to the multi-layered encryption approach and hardware-based memory protection.
2. **Authentication and Access Control:** Data custodians maintain control over who can provision input data and access results through certificate-based authentication and cryptographically enforced access policies.

3. **Verifiable Logic:** Data is only decrypted for software explicitly specified in advance, with reproducible builds enabling verification of the exact code running in the enclave.
4. **Remote Attestation:** Compliance with security policies can be cryptographically verified remotely, ensuring the entire system operates as expected.

These guarantees collectively ensure that even if an attacker gained complete control of the cloud infrastructure, they would be unable to access or modify sensitive data without detection.

This comprehensive security architecture allows iCARE4CVD to enable collaborative analysis of sensitive health data while maintaining privacy and regulatory compliance, addressing the central challenge of securely sharing sensitive data across institutional boundaries.

5 Results

The architecture with the main elements described in the previous section has been implemented and it is accessible via the Cohort Explorer Repository <https://github.com/MaastrichtU-IDS/cohort-explorer> . In this repository, installation instructions, the code and all technical documentation can be found.

The current ontology of iCARE4CVD is shared in the following repository. <https://maastrichtu-ids.github.io/cohort-explorer>

To enable testing by the consortium members to interact with the platform, the platform is made accessible via the iCARE4CVD webpage <https://explorer.icare4cvd.eu>

5.1 COHORT EXPLORER DEMO

Following our data sharing agreements, the consortium partners have provided several cohorts that could be used to develop the iCARE4CVD framework. This section is aimed at DEMO-ing the platform by showing the steps involved in the Cohort Explorer:

1. Exploring Cohorts:

The Cohort Explorer shows the overview of the cohorts. A researcher can browse existing cohorts in the system, they it can filter them by various characteristics or can search cohorts for specific variables or endpoints. The researcher explores the UM CHF dataset. This cohort has already mapped, and it is ready to be used by researchers. The screenshot below (Fig.8) shows the main “Explore” window, with the cohort overview on the right and the filtering options on the left.

Fig: 8 Cohort Explorer Overview

Clicking on one of the cohorts displays the metadata of that cohort, including the study objective and the variables collected for that cohort (Fig 9).

Fig: 9 Overview of a specific cohort

2. Addition of new Cohorts:

Fig 10 shows how the Cohort Explorer can be used to add a new cohort. To do this, the data owner adds the metadata dictionary for their cohort to the Cohort Explorer. The CDE Mapper usually has already been used to map the concepts as at this stage, the process is not fully automated. In the future, CDE Mapper can be fully integrated into the Cohort Explorer so that users can call it autonomously. Currently, the admin of Cohort Explorer makes sure that the use of the CDE Mapper is optimised by calling it when data dictionaries are complete.

Data dictionaries, when added to the Cohort Explorer go through a validation process that takes place to make sure the added metadata contains the required columns (e.g. "VARIABLE NAME" and "VARIABLE LABEL", etc.), check the types and values of those columns, etc. This step helps catch potential errors early and helps ensure uniformity in structure among the different cohorts' metadata dictionaries. The screenshots below show an example of this process. In the first screenshot, the data owner of the Aachen HF study uploads the Data Dictionary of the cohort. The upload attempt of the data dictionary fails. Two errors are indicated in the cohort explorer front-end (1 wrong datatype, 2, insufficient category information). When the data owner fixes the errors in the data dictionary, and re-uploads the file, the dictionary is accepted and gets added to the Cohort Explorer.

Fig: 10: Uploading a New Cohort. For this the data owner needs to prepare a data dictionary file.

3. Mapping a new Cohort:

When a metadata dictionary is added, a button appears next to each variable that displays the mapping options for that variable based on the OHDSI vocabulary (See Fig 1). The mapping window displays the name of each

OHDSI concept, its domain, its ID, and the number of other studies that use the concept. The screenshot below shows an example for the concepts identified automatically for the variable "Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration". This process is used to further check the mappings, especially if the CDE Mapper was involved in earlier steps.

Name	Domain	ID	Used by
Mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration determination	Measurement	snomedct:4290193	0
Mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration within reference range	Measurement	snomedct:4013244	0
Mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration above reference range	Measurement	snomedct:4013520	0
Mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration below reference range	Measurement	snomedct:4013083	0
Mean cell hemoglobin concentration - finding	Measurement	snomedct:4267514	0
Mean corpuscular hemoglobin determination	Measurement	snomedct:4182871	0
MCHC (erythrocyte mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration) calculation technique	Observation	snomedct:42536361	0
MCHC - Mean corpuscular haemoglobin concentration	Measurement	snomedct:37393850	0
Mean corpuscular hemoglobin below reference range	Measurement	snomedct:4013240	0
Mean corpuscular hemoglobin outside reference range	Measurement	snomedct:4013081	0
Mean corpuscular hemoglobin above reference range	Measurement	snomedct:4013241	0
Mean corpuscular hemoglobin within reference range	Measurement	snomedct:4013239	0
MCH (erythrocyte mean corpuscular hemoglobin) calculation technique	Observation	snomedct:42536362	0
Erythrocyte mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration Fetus Hematology and Cell counts	Measurement	loinc:37051976	0
Reticulocyte corpuscular hemoglobin concentration mean Blood Hematology and Cell counts	Measurement	loinc:37037428	0

Fig: 11: Using the Cohort Explorer to Map Variables

4. Upload the new cohort in DCR:

Once the data clean room for the cohort is created, the Data owner can upload the data directly to the Decentriq platform (See Fig 12). Inside the DCR, the upload process involves locally encrypting the data with a locally generated encryption key only known to them. The encrypted data is then uploaded to the Decentriq platform. Once encrypted and uploaded, the data can be analysed computationally but cannot be viewed or accessed in anyway.

Fig: 12: An example of the view provided in the DCR. The list of Data Owners has been redacted from the image for privacy concerns.

5. Selecting Cohorts for Analysis:

Using the cohort explorer the researcher can browse the cohorts and their variables. The researcher can:

- Filter by cohorts and by variable. As an example, a search for variables related to "creatinine" is performed. The variable is further explored to show the details.
- Select variables of interest from a cohort. As an example, the researcher selects weight, gender and an outcome variable from Aachen HF and UM CHF cohort.
- Create the DCR with weight, gender and outcome variable in Decentriq. Through the Cohort Explorer Frontend, the user is connected to the DCR created in Decentriq.

6. Creating computations:

The selected data is provisioned in a DCR. The researcher creates computation nodes to combine the two datasets, explore and analyse the data. Once the computation nodes are created, the data owner of the two cohorts (Aachen HF and UM CHF) will need to approve them.

7. Analysis and results

Once the data owners approve the nodes requested by the researcher, they become a part of the DCR, meaning that they can now be executed on the encrypted data and generate results. The results of the computations are shown to the researcher (See Fig 13).

Fig: 13: An example of computation (code for data analysis) within the DCR

The first time a Data Owner creates their DCR and provisions the data, an initial computation is performed on the data to: check for discrepancies between the data dictionary and the data and to identify some additional statistics which can be provided as meta-data to the cohort explorer. Once the computation concludes, some of the results are fed back into the interface of the Cohort Explorer. Those elements are (a) the summary statistics for each variable, and (b) visualization for the distribution of each collected variable. In the interface, clicking on the graph icon next to any variable brings up a window with that information. Examples can be found in Fig. 14.

Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration at BL Distribution

Summary Stats for MCHC_BL

```

Column: mchc_bl
Label: Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin
Concentration at BL
Type: Numeric (encoded as float64)
Number of non-null observations: 619
Number of Unique Values/Categories: 418
Mean: 33.20
Median: 33.18
Mode: 34.05
Std Dev: 1.20
Variance: 1.44
Range: 8.42
Q1: 32.50
Q3: 34.05
IQR: 1.55
Count empty: 3 (0.48%)
Count missing: 0 (0.00%)
Outliers (IQR): 12 (1.93%)
Outliers (Z): 1
Skewness: -0.13
Kurtosis: 0.65
W_Test: 0.99
Normality Test: p-value=0.0114 =>
Non-Normal
    
```

Distribution of MCHC_BL

Amount of days to First Gout AE adverse event Distribution

Summary Stats for FIRSTGOUTAE

```

Column: firstgoutae
Label: Amount of days to First Gout AE
adverse event
Type: Numeric (encoded as float64)
Number of non-null observations: 64
Number of Unique Values/Categories: 59
Mean: 195.47
Median: 127.00
Mode: 6.00
Std Dev: 175.83
Variance: 30914.73
Range: 560.00
Q1: 54.00
Q3: 305.25
IQR: 251.25
Count empty: 558 (89.71%)
Count missing: 0 (0.00%)
Outliers (IQR): 0 (0.00%)
Outliers (Z): 0
Skewness: 0.69
Kurtosis: -0.74
W_Test: 0.89
Normality Test: p-value=0.0000 =>
Non-Normal
    
```

Distribution of FIRSTGOUTAE

Fig: 14: Examples of statistical metadata for a specific variable in an iCARE4CVD cohort

5.2 LAYER 1: AUTOMATIC MAPPING OF COHORT VARIABLES (CDE MAPPER) RESULTS

The CDE-Mapper was analysed with 4 different datasets which varied in size, annotation type, and the presence of composite CDEs. The evaluation involved comparing CDE-Mapper (using Llama3.1, GPT4o-mini, and GPT4) against several state-of-the-art baseline models: SapBERT, KRIS BERT, BioBERT-snomed, and PromptLink. The primary evaluation metric was **accuracy at top-1 (acc@1)**, reflecting the

accuracy of the top-ranked prediction. Additionally, **Normalized Cumulative Gain Difference (NCGD)** was used to assess the ranking performance of the retrieved candidates. Ablation studies were conducted to understand the contribution of individual components like query decomposition and knowledge filtering. The performance was also analysed based on different CDE types (atomic, dependent, and composite) The query decomposition module was evaluated using precision, recall, and F1 score for attribute and value extraction, with manual curation by domain experts as the ground truth. The retrieval performance with different configurations (ensemble retrieval with and without knowledge filtering, with and without context-awareness) was assessed using accuracy at k (acc@k). The two-step reranking mechanism's effectiveness was evaluated by comparing accuracy before and after each reranking step. A case study further illustrated the framework's performance in handling complex CDEs, rare conditions, and ambiguous terminologies compared to baseline models, with evaluations against both ground truth and clinician assessments. Statistical significance was assessed using a T-test. **The results are shown in the table below:**

Models	NCBI-DC	BC5CDR-D	MIID	HF Studies
SapBERT	83.2	86.2	72.9	77.2
KRISS BERT	81	83	50.7	58.9
BioBERT-snomed	80.1	84.8	64.5	39.2
PromptLink	-	-	77.5	-
CDE-Mapper(Llama3.1)	94.4	88.2	80.2	86.4
CDE-Mapper (GPT4o-mini)	93.3	88.6	79.2	85.2
CDE-Mapper (GPT4)	88.1	88.3	79.3	83.2

Table 2: Performance comparison of CDE-Mapper variants and baseline models on concept linking tasks. datasets include NCBI-DC, BC5CDR-D, and HF Studies for linking to controlled vocabularies, as well as MIID for linking MIMIC-IV concepts to IBKH knowledge base. Results are presented as accuracy at top-1 (acc@1). - Denotes unavailable results from baseline. Statistically significant improvements (†) are noted compared to both baseline models and other CDE-Mapper variants using different LLMs (T-test, $\rho < 0.05$).

5.3 LAYER 1: ONTOLOGY RESULTS

We used the ontology based populated knowledge graph for downstream tasks of finding mappings between two studies namely TIME-CHF (65 variables) and GISSI-HF (1400 +). For this task, we developed a pipeline which used hybrid similarity technique where semantic similarity via text and graph traversal is applied to knowledge graphs of both studies. The preliminary results indicate the matching of more than 30 variables across studies as shown in Table 3.

TIME-CHF (source)	GISSI-HF (target)
large liver	large liver
spironolactone	spironolactone
nitroglycerin	Nitrate indicated
systolic blood pressure	systolic blood pressure

beta adrenergic receptor antagonist	Bisoprolol, carvedilol, metoprolol
c reactive protein [mass/volume] in serum or plasma by high sensitivity method	c reactive protein [mass/volume] in serum or plasma by high sensitivity method
diastolic blood pressure	diastolic blood pressure
creatinine [mass/volume] in serum or plasma	creatinine [mass/volume] in serum or plasma
age	age
body weight	body weight
heart rate	heart rate
natriuretic peptide.b prohormone n-terminal [mass/volume] in serum or plasma	natriuretic peptide.b prohormone n-terminal [mass/volume] in serum or plasma
urate [mass/volume] in serum or plasma	urate [mass/volume] in serum or plasma
patient hospital number	patient identification number
respiratory crackles	respiratory crackles
loop diuretic	antiarrhythmic agent
new york heart association classification	new york heart association classification
troponin t.cardiac panel - serum or plasma by high sensitivity method	troponin t.cardiac panel - serum or plasma by high sensitivity method
beta adrenergic receptor antagonist	beta adrenergic receptor antagonist
angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitor	angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitor
sex assigned at birth	sex assigned at birth

Table 3: Sample Results of Variable Matching between two heart failure studies.

The ontology model proposed in iCARE4CVD will be continuously refined as additional data are provided. What is interesting is that the ontology can support also the integration with wearable and other data formats.

5.4 LAYER 2: MANAGING DATA SHARING WITH LUCE RESULTS

In the following, we present an analysis of the initial evaluation results comparing a mapping-based approach (baseline) with a bitwise encoding method (proposed) for encoding provider consent policies and requester access preferences on-chain. The evaluation is conducted on Ganache (local) and Amoy (testnet) to assess gas consumption across different execution environments. It is important to clarify that the reported gas costs do not reflect on-chain policy enforcement or access control decisions. Instead, they correspond to gas costs associated with state transitions, specifically those incurred during the initialization, updates, and on-chain storage of provider consent policies and requester access preferences within smart contracts. In what follows, we present the gas usage analysis for providers and requesters under two settings: (1) Single category – consent is recorded for a subset of diseases within a single ICD-10 category, and (2) Whole category – consent applies to all ICD-10 codes.

In the single-category setting, where a provider grants consent for diseases within a single ICD-10 category, gas costs in the baseline approach scale linearly with the number of diseases. As shown in Figure 15, at 0% disease coverage (i.e., no diseases included in the provider’s consent list), gas consumption remains $\sim 45 \times 10^3$ units on Ganache and $\sim 48 \times 10^3$ units on Amoy. However, as disease coverage increases, gas costs rise from 390×10^3 (20% coverage) to 1443×10^3 (100% coverage) on Ganache, and from 477×10^3 (20%) to 1421×10^3 (100%) on Amoy, highlighting the overhead introduced by per-entry storage and lookup operations in Solidity mappings. In contrast, the proposed bitwise encoding approach maintains a near-constant gas consumption of $\sim 48 \times 10^3$ units, achieving a 30 \times reduction in provider-side gas costs at 100% coverage. A similar pattern holds in the whole-category setting, where the provider consents to all diseases in the ICD-10 code set. As illustrated in Figure 16, at 0% disease coverage (i.e., no diseases included in the provider’s consent settings), gas consumption remains $\sim 45 \times 10^3$ units (Ganache) and $\sim 48 \times 10^3$ units (Amoy). However, when all ICD-10 diseases are included, gas costs in the baseline approach increase to 3.77×10^6 (Ganache) and 2.5×10^6 (Amoy), highlighting the inefficiency of storing each disease separately. By contrast, the proposed approach maintains a near-constant gas consumption of $\sim 336 \times 10^3$ units, reducing gas costs by a factor of 11 \times to 15 \times compared to the baseline.

Fig 15: Gas consumption for provider consent configuration as disease coverage increases in the single-category setting, where the percentage represents the proportion of diseases within a single ICD-10 category included in the provider’s consent settings, with gas usage measured on both Ganache (local) and Amoy (testnet), comparing the efficiency of the baseline and proposed approaches

Fig 16: Gas consumption for provider consent configuration as disease coverage increases in the whole-category setting, where the percentage represents the proportion of all ICD-10 diseases included in the provider’s consent settings, with gas usage measured on both Ganache (local) and Amoy (testnet), highlighting the efficiency differences between the baseline and proposed approaches

From the requester’s perspective, gas costs scale similarly to provider-side consent configurations when recording access preferences. In the single-category setting, where a requester specifies access preferences for diseases within a single ICD-10 category, gas consumption in the baseline approach increases linearly with the number of diseases. As shown in Figure 17, at 0% disease coverage (i.e., no diseases included in the requester’s access list), gas consumption is $\sim 73 \times 10^3$ units on both Ganache and Amoy. As disease coverage increases, gas costs rise to 107×10^3 units (20% coverage), 142×10^3 units (40% coverage), 177×10^3 units (60% coverage), 211×10^3 units (80% coverage), and 274×10^3 units (100% coverage) on both networks. This increase reflects the per-entry storage overhead in Solidity mappings, where each disease entry adds a new storage slot. In contrast, the proposed bitwise encoding approach maintains a near-constant gas consumption of $\sim 48 \times 10^3$ units, reducing requester-side gas costs by approximately $5.7\times$ at 100% coverage. In the whole-category setting, gas costs scale with the number of diseases as the requester records access preferences for all diseases in the ICD-10 code set. As illustrated in Figure 18, at 0% disease coverage (i.e., no diseases included in the requester’s access list), gas consumption remains $\sim 45 \times 10^3$ units on Ganache and $\sim 48 \times 10^3$ units on Amoy. As disease coverage increases, gas costs in the baseline approach grow from $10,485 \times 10^3$ units (20%) to $26,379 \times 10^3$ units (60%) and reach $37,744 \times 10^3$ units at 100% coverage on Ganache, while on Amoy, gas usage rises from $19,133 \times 10^3$ units (40%) to $25,000 \times 10^3$ units at 100%. This increase is attributed to per-entry storage operations in Solidity mappings, where each disease entry expands the storage state. In contrast, the proposed bitwise encoding approach maintains a near-constant gas consumption of $\sim 336 \times 10^3$ units, reducing requester-side gas costs significantly at all coverage levels relative to the baseline.

Fig 17: Gas consumption in requester consent recording as disease coverage increases, where the percentage represents the proportion of diseases within a single ICD-10 category included in the requester’s consent settings, with gas usage measured to compare the efficiency of the baseline and proposed approaches across Ganache and Amoy.

Fig 18: Gas consumption in requester consent recording as disease coverage increases, where the percentage represents the proportion of all possible disease categories included in the requester’s consent settings, with gas usage measured to compare the efficiency of the baseline and proposed approaches across Ganache and Amoy.

One of the primary factors contributing to the reduction in gas usage is the difference in how consent information is stored and updated. In the baseline approach, each disease is stored separately using a Solidity mapping, where every insertion results in a new key-value pair being persisted in contract storage. Since Solidity mappings do not impose a predefined structure, each disease entry occupies a distinct storage slot, thereby triggering a separate SSTORE operation (a storage write operation that modifies the blockchain state and incurs significant gas costs). As a result, gas costs scale linearly ($O(n)$) with the number of stored diseases due to the per-entry storage overhead. By contrast, the proposed bitwise encoding method represents multiple disease permissions within a fixed-length bitstring, enabling updates with a single SSTORE operation, thereby reducing per-entry storage costs and improving gas efficiency. The benefits of this optimization are evident across both provider and requester perspectives, as gas usage remains near constant regardless of disease coverage, whereas the baseline approach exhibits increasing costs due to the accumulation of storage updates. These results indicate that bitwise encoding provides a more scalable and cost-effective alternative for recording consent policies and access preferences in blockchain-based systems. Given its ability to maintain efficiency across different disease coverage levels, the proposed method is particularly applicable to iCARE4CVD, where managing extensive disease data in a gas-efficient manner is essential. Lastly, it is important to note that Ganache has been deprecated and is no longer maintained, while testnet gas costs do not accurately reflect those on the Ethereum mainnet due to differences in transaction fee structures, the absence of real economic incentives, and artificially low gas prices. As a result, while the results presented provide a comparative analysis of consent encoding strategies, the absolute gas costs measured on Ganache and Amoy should not be considered representative of mainnet deployment costs. [66]

6 Discussion

5.1 EXTENDING THE COHORT EXPLORER

The second version of the cohort explorer has been tested by data analysts working on the iCARE4CVD platform. We have been improving the solution based on their feedback. Yet, currently, the user base in the platform is still low. This is due to delays with the data sharing agreement needed to be in place for data providers to start uploading the data into Data Clean Rooms. To mitigate this issue, we have been using synthetic data generation to generate data based on the information provided in data dictionaries.

Furthermore, due to data providers having a hard time to identify the mappings, we provided a service (the CDE-Mapper) that can replace the manual mappings with automatic mappings where possible. For this we worked with Large Language and AI models (see section 4.2.2 and 5.2 for detailed information on this work).

The first iteration of our ontology model has been established to lay the foundational semantic framework for our cardiovascular project. This version delineates a preliminary set of classes and relationships that are pivotal to representing patient data, medical conditions, treatments, and healthcare interactions specific to iCARE4CVD use-cases. Next, we will focus on the following steps:

User Enrolment in the Cohort Explorer and DCR: Currently, we are slowly enrolling our partners into the DCR. We show them how to perform each step and support them if issues arise. This is important for testing of the iCARE4CVD platform and improvement in generalizing the enrolment process

Validation of the Ontology Model: Concurrent with the expansion of CDEs, we are initiating a rigorous validation process. This involves subjecting the ontology to a series of tests against real-world cardiovascular

datasets to ascertain its accuracy, consistency, and applicability. Through this validation, we seek to identify and rectify any discrepancies, ambiguities, or gaps within the model.

Dynamic Model: As we refine the ontology, our goal is to achieve a dynamic model that can evolve with the advancements in cardiovascular medicine. This involves continuous collaboration with domain experts, incorporation of feedback from end-users, and adherence to emerging standards in healthcare data exchange. Additionally, we plan to enable the ontology to support advanced analytics and machine learning algorithms, thereby contributing to predictive and prescriptive analytics in cardiovascular care.

Stakeholder Engagement: Throughout the development process, we are aiming to engage with a range of stakeholders, including ontology experts and health care specialists within project to ensure the ontology aligns with the practical needs and expectations of its users. By adopting an iterative and collaborative approach, we are committed to delivering an ontology model that is not only scientifically robust but also pragmatically valuable in the real-world setting of cardiovascular health management.

5.2 REPLICATING ANALYSIS IN DATA CLEAN ROOMS

Data clean rooms provide a secure environment where researchers can access and analyse sensitive data without compromising privacy or security. By implementing strict controls and protocols, such as anonymization techniques and access controls, clean rooms ensure that individual privacy is protected while enabling diverse research workflows.

ICARE4CVD has already implemented pipelines for data analysis in WP5. These pipelines will be further integrated into the platform and enable federated analysis into multiple cohorts.

Furthermore, in order to balance flexibility, privacy and security, several aspects of the workflow for data analysts and data owners are evolving with the course of the project. Such as:

1. **Getting access to data samples for script development:** Researchers have expressed the wish to have access to underlying data and be able to see such datasets, in order to develop their data analysis scripts. As this is not possible, due to privacy and security concerns by many data custodians, there are different ways in which Decentriq has enabled researchers to explore the data in a compliant way. For example, synthetic data generation is performed by the DCR on existing datasets. However, there is a concern for privacy with datasets that contain many variables belonging to very few people. Moreover, researchers have expressed the wishes to have “shuffled data”, which cannot be considered anonymous and is easily traceable to the individual patient. With the course of the project, we will assess the level of privacy and security required by GDPR and individual data custodians and provide features to enable more exploratory data analysis within these constraints.
2. **Dynamic consent management:** Currently data owners need to accept and or reject each computational request on the data. In our future developments, the blockchain we will study how to further simplify the management of consent based on pre-established rules by the data owner.
3. **Improving the API functionalities of DECENIRIQ platform:** The interaction between the cohort explorer and the DCR is performed from the Cohort Explorer API to the Decentriq API. Further improvements to the Decentriq API may be needed to bring it up-to date to the functionalities that the Decentriq Platform offers within its own front-end platform.

7 Conclusion

This deliverable presented the Architecture for iCARE4CVD, its main components and how they interrelate with one another to create the overall data federation. We keep further improving this model as more users are enrolled into the platform.

Annexes

Technical Factsheet

Bellow a technical summary of the architecture was provided by WP2 and send to all partners to understand the high-level work if WP2.

Having data is nice, but having useful data is essential!

WP1 and WP2 are closely collaborating to ensure that the consortium has access to useful and high-quality data. In WP1, we will curate relevant datasets and ensure they are ready to be used when our researchers need their questions answered. Data provided by members will be protected and only accessible by authorized individuals through the the multi-layered technical architecture built in WP2. The architecture will enable technical enforcement of the data management plan to facilitate compliance with data processing requirements.

A high-level overview of the target architecture

Our architecture has three components, each designed to protect patient data privacy while enabling flexible analysis (Fig. 1). LUCE Blockchain platform handles data permissions and holds data sharing agreements. The Cohort explorer UI based on knowledge graphs provides a unified interface for exploring cohorts on a meta-data level, making it easy for analysts to discover data. In the analysis layer, Decentriq Data Clean Rooms ensures secure data analysis while enabling regulatory compliance. Our architecture enables researchers to analyse data efficiently and securely while allowing partners providing data to maintain control over processing of such data and preserving patient privacy.

Figure 1. Technical Architecture Components

The user experience and implications

1. Users connect to the cohort explorer UI and create an account
2. They upload their data dictionary (metadata)
3. They get to the Decentriq environment where they get the encryption toolkit to connect their data to a Data Clean Room
4. Researchers form questions in the cohort explorer and analyse encrypted data in Data Clean Rooms
5. Data custodians approve the analyses.
6. Approved results are retrieved without the raw data ever being exposed or compromised.
7. Blockchain keeps an immutable track of everything that happened

For more information on the data protection and IT security implications please refer to [DCR Data Protection Whitepaper](#) or the [Joint Controllorship Agreement](#)

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